

Interrogating common-sense assumptions toward a more just mathematics education

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In this symposium participants will interrogate common sense assumptions that serve to (re)produce long standing inequities in mathematics education. “Common sense” is historically and culturally constructed, rather than a natural reflection of “the way things are.” Therefore, surfacing the historical roots of common-sense assumptions provides powerful opportunities to reframe problems of access, oppression, and erasure. We invite participants to consider common sense assumptions behind problems of equity in their own contexts, trace their histories, and offer alternative narratives to reframe these problems. We hope to better understand how common-sense assumptions have shaped mathematics education across the globe, and use these insights to reimagine mathematics education.

Aims of the symposium

In the context of a school year in which a horrific global pandemic and widespread racist violence have dominated the global discourse, we come together as a collective to question and reimagine a different world for mathematics education. In the U.S., at least, mathematics education, rooted in assimilationist labor, military-industrial, and capitalist agendas, has continued to play a significant role in perpetuating white supremacy in schooling practices, (Vossoughi & Vakil, 2018). Across Europe and around the world, research has argued that the simultaneous rise of neoliberalism and nationalism has resulted in educational policies in mathematics sustained by raced, gendered, and classed ideas of mastery, ability, and autonomous selfhood (e.g., Ineson & Povey, 2020). In this symposium, we explore how the practices of mathematics education rest on a set of assumptions, or a “common sense” that is historically and culturally, and politically constructed. Surfacing these common-sense assumptions, we argue, will provide opportunities to reframe the persistent problems of access, oppression, and erasure in mathematics education. The aim of this symposium is to invite participants to share and discuss common sense assumptions in their own contexts,

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then consider alternative narratives that may serve to reframe the problem space of mathematics education, thereby providing opportunities to ask new, more productive research questions and to reimagine how we design and take action for equitable teaching and learning.

In the following, we discuss what we mean by common sense assumptions and how they operate in our mathematics education scholarship and practice. We end with a description of proposed symposium activities.

Relevance of the symposium

Activists, mathematicians, and other scholars have highlighted the ways in which certain assumptions around mathematics have been deployed to support systems of oppression around the world (e.g., Wong, 2020). Mathematics education, which plays an exaggerated role in mediating the educational experiences and possibilities of students across the globe, has also been implicated in these conversations (e.g., Valero et al., 2012). For example, the discourse of “learning loss” presumes a particular set of knowledge must necessarily be acquired in each year of a child’s life, and that any deviation from this progression will produce detrimental effects. In response to concerns around students’ “learning loss” as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic, a host of responses have been proposed in the US, including the implementation of impractical and demonstrably inequitable standardized tests to measure “learning loss” while the pandemic continues to rage, and an increase of school hours and days in the next year (Ewing, 2020).

However, the very idea of “learning loss” hinges on common sense assumptions that include valuing a standardized yet arbitrary trajectory of achievement, as well as the insistence that the only learning of value occurs in school (McKinney de Royston & Vossoughi, 2021). We take up Schutz’s (1953) argument that common sense, while critical for the accomplishment of everyday activity and social order, is, in fact, historically and culturally constructed (Garfinkel, 1967). What is considered common sense in one context (e.g., taking off one’s shoes before entering homes is a common cultural practice in many communities) may seem absurd, or even offensive in another (e.g., guests from other communities may find it overly intimate to reveal their socked or bare feet). Common sense understandings also change across local contexts, including institutional spaces (e.g., one might expect to go to the bathroom when the need arises; in many school settings permission must be granted first) and disciplinary domains (e.g., some disciplinary conventions lead students to expect right and wrong answers, whereas others are presented as more flexible; Schutz, 1953).

Further, common sense understandings and assumptions serve to reproduce the cultures from which they originate. Garfinkel (1967) explained, “Not only does common sense knowledge portray a real society for members, but in the manner of a self-fulfilling prophecy the features of the real society are produced by persons’ motivated compliance with these background expectancies.... Seen from the person’s point of view, his commitments to motivated compliance consist of his grasp of and subscription to the ‘natural facts of life in

Interrogating common-sense assumptions toward a more just mathematics education society” (p. 53). It follows that the common-sense understandings on which the inequitable conditions of mathematics education have been built serve to reproduce these conditions. In our example of “learning loss,” we see how the common-sense assumptions about where valuable learning occurs and standardized achievement expectations bolsters the discourse of “learning loss,” which in turn perpetuates inequitable practices like standardized testing and reifies the importance of normative, factory style schooling practices.

We argue that illuminating the historical origins and cultural development of these common-sense assumptions may allow us to understand anew the problem space of mathematics education. As Schutz (1953) notes, “all cultural objects--tools, symbols, language systems, works of art, social institutions, etc.--point back by their very origin and meaning to the activities of human subjects [...]. This historicity is capable of being examined in its reference to human activities of which it is the sediment” (Schutz, 1953, p. 3). There is a relationship between these histories and how they have sedimented in contemporary society. For our learning loss example, we can trace some of this discourse in the U.S. to the history of standardization of public education. Tyack and Tobin (1994) described how sorting classrooms into age-determined grade levels was an invention which, while commonplace today, did not become so until the twentieth century. Inspired by specialization and division of labor practices in factories, reformers from universities and state departments of education wanted to increase both efficiency of and control over public education. In a related effort, school content was divided into narrowly defined subject areas with required sequences, and tests were administered to determine whether students could advance to the next grade. While fears over learning loss is sensible within this context, examination of the context itself reveals a commitment to the needs of university reformers and politicians over concerns about, for example, the wellbeing of children, their teachers, and their communities. Considering this (simplified, for the purposes of this proposal) history of standardized, graded schooling in the U.S. allows us to reframe “the problem” of learning loss as many different problems, such as grade level standardization, whose knowledge counts in curricular sequences, and the role of efficiency in policy decisions in education.

Format of the symposium

This symposium is designed to support participant discussion and collective learning. The co-authors of the symposium will begin by introducing the concept of common-sense assumptions and provide the example of learning loss described above. The remainder of the symposium will support small group discussions of “a problem” related to mathematics education in participants’ local contexts. In discussion, groups will unpack the common-sense assumptions required for defining “the problem” in a particular manner, and delineate the political and social premises from which these assumptions operate. As a consequence, these investigations will transform the problem space, allowing small groups to articulate different problems that may be addressed, expanding possibilities for reimagining mathematics education.

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